

Личностные и средовые детерминанты рискованного поведения обучающихся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья

Е. В. СЕМЕНОВА, Г. К. ТРУФАНОВА, С. Н. БЕЗДЕТКО

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Страны-участники Саммита ООН (16 – 19 сентября 2022 г., Нью-Йорк) подчеркивают разрушительное воздействие глобального кризиса равенства и инклюзивности на будущее детей и молодежи во всем мире, актуализируя проблемы инклюзии и обеспечения равного доступа к образованию в глобальной политической повестке. Участники Саммита призывают заложить фундамент трансформации образования на основе реализации принципов инклюзивности, создания недискриминационных, комфортных условий, обеспечивающих психологическое благополучие всех субъектов образовательной среды.

Цель статьи – выявить, рассмотреть и представить теоретическое обоснование детерминант рискованного поведения обучающихся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья в инклюзивной образовательной среде на основе анализа научных подходов к изучению влияния средовых и личностных детерминант на психологическое благополучие обучающихся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья.

Материалы и методы. Исследование выполнено на основе обзора и анализа содержания научных публикаций, представленных в международной научной базе PubMed, а также статей, входящих в Российский индекс научного цитирования и представленных в электронной библиотеке e-library. Применялись такие методы, как анализ источников по проблеме исследования, сопоставление и обобщение подходов к изучению личностных и средовых детерминант рискованного поведения у обучающихся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья.

Результаты исследования. Обучающиеся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья различных нозологий в силу имеющихся нарушений психофизического развития оказываются наиболее психологически уязвимой группой детей в среде образовательных организаций, реализующих инклюзивную практику. Для оценки личностных и средовых детерминант рискованного поведения, предикторов психологического неблагополучия детей с особыми образовательными потребностями необходимо учитывать их психофизиологические, когнитивные, социальные, психологические характеристики и содержание компонентов инклюзивной образовательной среды, уникальным образом проявляющееся в каждой конкретной школе.

Заключение. Результат анализа средовых и личностных детерминант рискованного поведения детей с ОВЗ может являться отправной точкой при планировании и проектировании профилактической и коррекционно-педагогической работы с детьми и подростками с целью предупреждения, нивелирования или снижения проявлений рискованного поведения.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

обучающиеся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья, инклюзивная образовательная среда, рискованное поведение, средовые детерминанты, личностные детерминанты, профилактика рискованного поведения, психологическое благополучие

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Personal and environmental determinants of risk behaviour of students with disabilities

E. V. SEMENOVA, G. K. TRUFANOVA, S. N. BEZDETKO

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The participating countries of the UN Summit (16–19 September 2022, New York) point to the devastating impact of the global crisis of equity and inclusivity on the future of children and young people around the world, bringing the issues of inclusion and equal access to education to the top of the global policy agenda. The Summit participants call for laying the foundation for the transformation of education based on the principles of inclusivity as well as the creation of non-discriminatory, comfortable conditions ensuring the psychological well-being of all subjects of the educational environment.

The article aims to identify, consider and present a theoretical justification of determinants of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment on the basis of the analysis of scientific approaches to studying the impact of environmental and personal determinants on the psychological well-being of challenged students.

Materials and methods. The research was implemented on the basis of reviewing and analysing the content of scientific publications presented in the international scientific database PubMed, as well as a number of articles included in the Russian Science Citation Index and presented in the electronic library e-Library. The authors used the following methods in their research: analysis of sources on the research problem, comparison and generalisation of approaches to the study of personal and environmental determinants of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities.

Results. Students with disabilities of various nosology types, for the reason of psychophysical development disorders, turn out to be the most psychologically vulnerable group of children in the environment of educational organisations engaged in inclusive practice. To assess the personal and environmental determinants of risk behaviour and predictors of psychological distress of children with special educational needs, it is necessary to take into account their psychophysiological, cognitive, social and psychological characteristics along with the content of inclusive educational environment components uniquely manifested in any school.

Conclusion. The result of analysing the environmental and personal determinants of risk behaviour of children with health limitations can be a starting point in planning and designing preventive and corrective pedagogical work with children and adolescents aimed to prevent, counter-balance or reduce the manifestations of risk behaviour.

KEYWORDS

students with disabilities, inclusive educational environment, risk behaviour, environmental determinants, personal determinants, prevention of risk behaviour, psychological well-being

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INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organisation, about 16% of the world's population (1.3 billion people) have some form of disability. This group of people is more often exposed to risk factors of various addictions (alcohol use, etc.), including psychological factors associated with stigmatisation and discrimination. Given the prevalence of health and life activity constraints, the issues of social inclusion, the formation of inclusive culture in society, and the impact of the inclusive educational environment, in particular, on the psychological well-being of learners with disabilities, become particularly relevant in the context of the global transformation of education.

A priority direction in the development of inclusive education is the creation of conditions for emotional well-being of learners with health limitations as educational environment subjects in the process of their psychological and pedagogical support. In this regard, the problem of studying personal and environmental determinants of behavioural disorders in childhood seems to be much relevant.

According to some researchers (as expounded in the works by Sleptsova and Vezhik, Spasojević et al.), an inclusive educational environment is a "special unit of social environment" characterised by a specific structure and content that make it possible to handle the problems of co-education of different categories of students, in particular, those with special education needs (learners with disabilities) and normotypically developing peers [17; 41].

An educational environment is defined by Yasvin as a system of "conditions affecting the formation of a personality, as well as a set of opportunities for learners' self-development offered by the social and spatial/objective environment" [25]. Coelho et al. note that an inclusive educational environment contains opportunities for the manifestation of a subjective position of any learner, including a child with special education needs [26]. According to Fitzgerald and Radford, a student with disabilities, being a subject of an educational environment, enters into interaction with other actors – normotypical learners, teachers, parents; succumbs to their influence and, in turn, influences them [30].

The problem addressed from the perspective of theoretical research focuses on identifying the components of an inclusive educational environment and the factors that affect the psychological well-being of learners with disabilities in this environment [43]. In this case, psychological distress is considered to be a predictor of the risk behaviour of learners of the explored category [9]. In the practical aspect, the determinants of risk behaviour identified in an inclusive educational environment in relation to challenged students are defined as guidelines for preventive psychological and pedagogical work in educational organisations implementing inclusive practice.

The work aimed to specify groups of factors affecting the psychological well-being of learners with health limitations in an inclusive educational environment, and to consider the special impact of these factors in the context of specifics of psychophysical development of the target group children, as well as to explore the environment of educational organisations engaged in inclusive practice.

The outlined research goal was achieved by selecting scientific sources and articles exploring the environmental and personal determinants of risk behaviour. The use of different methods of analysis, synthesis and comparison of scholarly data served to searching for an answer to the questions: "What factors, conditions and components of an inclusive educational environment can serve as determinants of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities? Are these factors specific (manifested exclusively in an inclusive environment) in relation to students with different developmental disabilities? How is this specificity manifested? "

The object of the study is environmental and personal determinants of risk behaviour; the subject of the research is the specifics of manifestation of these determinants in learners with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment.

METHODS

The data explored in the study were selected by reviewing and analysing the content of publications presented in the international scientific database PubMed, as well as publications included in the Russian Science Citation Index and presented in the electronic library eLibrary. The words "behavioural disorders", "risk behaviour determinants", "causes of behavioural disorders" and "personality" were used as keywords for the search. After the search and formation of a database for the scholarly review, a number of publications were selected that contained information relevant for the research topic. These include, for instance, articles in the scientific journals *Collection of Humanitarian Research*, *Special Education*, *Pedagogical Education in Russia*, *Open Journal of Social Sciences* and others.

RESULTS

McLaughlin interprets the educational environment from the position of the social approach to defining the concept of "education" – as a social system with its inherent elements: emotional climate, personal well-being of the environment actors, features of the microculture, and quality of the educational process [19].

The researchers exploring the phenomenon of an educational environment (Klimov, Kovalev, Tyurin, etc.) distinguish the following components and parameters of the educational environment: social/communicative, informational, somatic, and objective. The social/communicative aspect of the environment is characterised by the relationships between the educational environment actors, the features of their activities, lifestyles, behaviour, social experience and culture. Some significant aspects of the social/communicative component of the educational environment include characteristics of learners' and teachers' communities, along with the specification of a person's place in a given group and his/her affiliation with different groups.

When identifying the determinants of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities, the somatic component of the educational environment is preemptive since it considers the training process actors' states, implies the use of health-saving and adaptive technologies by teachers and the presence of positive emotional and psychological climate in the environment [6].

The information-specific component of an inclusive educational environment is secured by unimpeded access of learners with disabilities to the information resources of the educational organisation and accessibility of visual aids used in the educational institution for persons with special education needs. The objective component of the educational environment includes material, technical, physical, biological and other conditions [15].

The features of an educational, including inclusive, environment are determined by the specifics of a particular educational organisation in which this environment is formed. The characteristics showing specific, unique features of a particular educational environment include the level of corporate culture, team spirit, the extent of the participants' cohesion, the existence of groups and associations within the community, the level of learners' protection in the team and their place in large and small social groups [34].

In a broad sense, the educational environment can be represented by internal and external factors. Internal environmental factors are manifested through relationships between the educational process actors. The external environment is understood as a subject's physical and social environment. External and internal environmental factors cumulatively influence the child's personality, physical, intellectual and spiritual development [17].

The authors of the present article support Lomov's position who accentuates the systemic nature of determinacy of mental phenomena and personal development, which implies the inclusion of external and internal factors, general and special preconditions and mediating links in their structure.

According to the researcher, personality behaviour determinants are represented by a set of prerequisites, conditions, factors and properties conditioning the ways of formation and manifestation of a particular behaviour [13].

As concerns personal determinants of risk behaviour, Popov's opinion is worthy of attention – he points out that external and internal determinants serve as psychological regulators of personal behaviour. The internal determinants, according to the author, include psychological features of a personality, value orientations, personal attitudes and motivational sphere [16].

Zmanovskaya systematises and describes the sources of behavioural disorders in childhood and adolescence. The author, from the position of personal development, refers the following features to such factors: individual susceptibility and vulnerability, the personality's difficulties or dysfunction of self-regulation, and his/her attitude to a particular form of behavioural disorder, including risk behaviour, and deficiency of personal resources [8].

Finnish researchers Romppanen et al. undertook a long-term survey involving 192 adolescents. The data were collected by interviewing adolescents, their mothers and fathers. Subsequently, at the second phase, when the interviewed adolescents reached adulthood, the same respondents were surveyed again. In their study, the authors proved the relationship between adolescents' social competence and their adaptive functioning in the future. In particular, adolescents with a high level of social competence show fewer manifestations of internalising disorders in the future [29].

Nemattavousi notes in his works that alexithymia and disorders of emotional regulation lead to difficulties in adapting to traumatic situations and the accumulation of negative emotions [35].

Myasishchev, noting that behavioural disorders are a result of a complex tangle of biological and social factors, emphasises the importance of studying the child's personality and assessing the role of his/her attitude to reality and the dynamics of such relationship in terms of abnormal childhood [14].

The personal determinants of risk behaviour in children with health limitations are conditioned by the structure of disorders within each nosological group. Adolescents with disabilities, as a special social group, have difficulties in analysing and organising their behaviour due to developmental peculiarities.

The majority of children with health limitations are characterised by a pace lag in the formation of cognitive and speech development – on the condition that their intelligence is intact. For instance, Shneider notes that self-cognition, conceptualisation of the surrounding world and other people, analysis of behavioural patterns and moral evaluation of behavioural acts by children with disabilities significantly differs from that in normotypical peers [23]. In addition, the intellectual development of children with disabilities, regardless of belonging to a particular nosological group, is characterised by qualitative specifics of the maturity of their cognitive functions. They show difficulties in processing, comprehension and preservation of information coming from the environment, and difficulties in establishing cause-and-effect relationships. All this leads to insufficient meaningfulness of the forming behaviour, immaturity of ideas about its alternative forms, which increases the likelihood of various manifestations of risk behaviour.

The structure of personal determinants of risk behaviour includes individual psychological features of children with health limitations. The probability of risk behaviour formation is enhanced by several features of personal development of children with developmental disorders – heightened impulsiveness, irritability, and hyperactivity conditioned by the functioning of the nervous system. At the same time, it should be noted that these features are poorly controllable by children and determine the nature of their behaviour.

Relevant studies show that all children with disabilities have emotional and volitional disorders in the structure of the defect. Acute emotional response, inadequate reactions, neurasthenia and borderline states can be caused by psychopathies or character accentuations, which, in turn, negatively affects the children's behaviour and may be a cause of proneness to risk in

adolescence. Inadequate self-esteem is a feature characteristic of most children with disabilities, manifested along with other emotional and volitional disorders. Against this background, frequently occurring situations of frustration are an important factor in the formation of risk behaviour. In such situations, children, to meet their needs in accordance with their expectations, often show demonstrative behaviour, which can reach risky forms in case of a positive payoff. Modern foreign research also adheres to this view. For instance, Colmsee et al. point to low self-esteem as one of the determinants of behavioural disorders. Their study involving adolescent girls proves that low self-esteem is a universal risk factor for the development of various eating disorders, as evidenced by the statistical data: $r = -.23$, $p = -.09$ [27].

High risk indicators for victimisation of children with limited health capacities deserve special attention. Some expressed features of self-cognition and self-perception, a low level of mental integrity, infantilism, increased suggestibility, and disharmony in relationships with others are prerequisites for the formation of victimising behaviour in this category of children which, in turn, manifests itself in the form of psychological, moral and social deformation fixed in their behaviour [0].

Leontiev's studies prove the dependence of the psychological well-being of persons with disabilities on the distinct manifestation of their personal resources. However, none of the psychological resources described by the author (mental strength resources, self-regulation and instrumental resources, motivational and conceptual resources) is fully formed in challenged children, which aggravates their psychological well-being, reduces adaptive functions and increases the likelihood of various forms of risk behaviour [12].

Alekhina et al. [1], Megapanou [33], Li and Omar [32] draw attention to the need for support and activity on the part of actors involved in interaction with challenged students as key characteristics of an inclusive educational environment in the context of its system-forming component. In their opinion, the support provided to a learner with disabilities by participants in educational relations and the extent of the former's participation turns the environment conditions into opportunities for the educational activity of its actors. In this case, participation is understood, in the first place, as "students' activity in construction of their individual educational routes, independent choice of extracurricular work, awareness of their interests and difficulties, and a realised need for necessary types of support" [1].

The studies by Paseka and Schwab explore and analyse the experience of educational administrators in creating a potential for inclusive education involving systematic literature reviewing [38]. Detailed analysis enables one to understand the current trends in inclusive education in school environment.

Inclusive education orientates educators towards the inclusion of learners with disabilities in the educational process based on the organisation of training under adapted basic educational programmes, flexible variation of different forms of classroom and extracurricular activities, adaptation of teaching materials and realisation of the correctional education principle. In particular, a survey by Zabeli and Gjelij presents some data obtained through personal interviewing of preschool teachers devoted to the issues of inclusive education [44]. Inclusion requires educators to change and adjust pedagogical actions to meet the special needs of children with disabilities. This serves to changes in the content and quality of social, informational, objective and other components and education environment parameters.

The teachers' competence formation problems in the field of inclusive education are presented in a study by Bezdetko et al. [4]. The article authors note that quite many teachers working at general education institutions have difficulties in organising learning interaction between children in the classroom, failing to apply proper ways of adapting the curriculum content and teaching material in specific subjects [4]. Not all educators are able to work with proper technologies for the organisation of learning in an inclusive classroom and creation of spatial and temporal conditions for teaching a child with disabilities; they have not been trained in the methods of work covering all students despite the diversity of special educational needs and ways of providing support; in addition, they lack conflict prevention skills.

A study by Graham and Spandagou presents the results of studying primary school principals' perceptions of inclusive education in New South Wales, Australia. The principals' attitudes towards inclusive education and their success in developing inclusive practices depend largely on their own perception of the notion of "inclusivity" as well as the attitudes and capabilities of the involved teachers [31].

An inclusive educational environment is not always psychologically safe for adolescents with disabilities. The research results indicate that physically challenged learners and children with disabilities are more exposed to the risk of violence against them than their physically and intellectually healthy peers (Astakhova, Buslaeva) [3]. Children and adolescents with special developmental needs are at risk with respect to factors involving psychological insecurity.

A student with disabilities immersed in an inclusive educational environment is psychologically the most vulnerable and defenceless. When determining the strategies of preventive and remedial pedagogical work, it is advisable for the educational psychologist of a training organisation to analyse the current environmental factors and personal determinants that condition the motives and hazards of risk behaviour.

When organising preventive work, it is important not to take a formal approach to compliance with the statutory requirements for the creation of a barrier-free inclusive environment, but, in the first place, to engage in profound preliminary work to prepare the social environment of the educational organisation for acceptance and active involvement of learners with disabilities in a positive-minded team (group, class) and joint activities.

We share the position of Ulyanova and Popova who note that children's risk behaviour causes a need for personal support that includes individual programmes and a set of special methods and means of psychological and pedagogical assistance. Characterising risk behaviour, the authors draw attention not only to the learner's activity but also to his/her possible passivity, as viewed from the pedagogical point of view (a person's disengagement, estrangement from communication with others, etc.) [20, p. 347]. Children's risk behaviour as a pedagogical phenomenon considered in the context of the humanistic pedagogical paradigm provides the realisation of a personality-centred and system-integrative approach to the organisation of the pedagogical process.

Preventive work assumes active cooperation of all actors directly and indirectly involved in upbringing and education of the younger generation. A special role is assigned to parents (legal representatives) of learners with disabilities.

According to Sutan and Mahat, Paseka and Schwab, special attention is paid to working with the family of a challenged student [38; 42]. The research in the field of interaction of the educators and the family of a child with disabilities makes it possible to choose due models and stages of intercommunion with the parents (legal representatives).

Chubarovsky stresses the importance of risk behaviour prevention for the identification and formation of high-risk groups [22]. The purpose of socio-pedagogical primary prevention technologies is to provide objective information about the consequences of various risky behaviour types for human's physical, mental and social well-being, and about the possible assistance in case of problems. Socio-pedagogical technologies are understood by Chubarovsky as alternative leisure programmes for young people along with other forms of educational and extracurricular activities of a training organisation.

One of the technologies aimed at the integration of learners with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment is mentoring [10]. For instance, the formation of schoolmasterly pairs "a learner with normotypical development – a learner with disabilities" contributes to the establishment of friendly relations between the children and forms the awareness of security, worthiness, appreciation and acceptance in the environment on this basis. The physically challenged child's ability to express the subjective position, as well as his/her self-realisation, is formed in various types of joint activities with the children in the group: creative, academic and sportive. Quests serve as a

method of forming interaction between the educational environment actors [11]; however, they are used not for creating competition between the participants but for team building, children's rallying, and the formation of the ability to negotiate and handle group problems jointly.

Correa et al. highlight some factors that can influence the behaviour of children with disabilities [28]. The environmental factors that affect the challenged child's personality can be represented in any of the above components of an inclusive educational environment. For instance, a student may experience loneliness, abandonment, worthlessness in the school environment if the learners' team does not accept him/her or if the teaching staff or the form master does not provide the necessary support and concern.

Situations of chronic failure at school are potentially risky for a challenged student making him/her feel psychologically unsafe. The feeling of helplessness in academic performance, a fear of making mistakes when answering a question or answering incorrectly, being afraid of getting a bad assessment mark or meeting disapproval on the part of a teacher and classmates – all of this can be a cause of anxiety for a learner with disabilities. A special child immersed in an inclusive educational environment can feel anxiety, despair, helplessness in handling learning tasks if the teachers and parents make excessive demands on his/her academic performance, or expectations that do not match the child's actual learning abilities.

In these terms, the content of the pedagogical team's preventive work shall be aimed at mastering the methods of adaption of the instructional tutorials and the ways of presenting the material that are accessible for the perception of any learner; it should involve due development and use of memos, schemes and general templates for meeting the assignments; stepwise algorithms of compliance with academic instructions, visual guidelines, etc. for the use in the class. The teacher is advised to take into account the pace of the learner's activity at the lesson, to grant him/her additional time to complete the work and the opportunity not to complete the entire assignment but present only a fragment or a specific part of it. Such techniques will help a challenged child to navigate better in the structure of the assignment, to better understand its main point and handling methods, not to worry that he/she will not have time to comply with the task or will not be able to execute it as proper. The extent of anxiety caused by the feeling of helplessness and foreboding of another failure will gradually fade when the child realises that he/she is able to cope with manageable, accessible tasks. It is important that the teacher reacts to the child's difficulties in the process of performing tasks in an emotionally calm manner.

An inclusive educational environment excludes value judgements emphasising the child's helplessness, or focusing on his/her failures; any attempts to "match" the challenged child's pace with the general progress of the class are unacceptable. The teacher's aggressive position of this nature can provoke the peers' negative attitude towards a learner with disabilities.

Gerasimenko and Adushkina, describing preventive work with risk behaviours, point to a number of training forms in combination with situation modelling methods, while paying attention to quests, sports games, discussions, etc. The advantage of the programme proposed by the authors is its focus on comprehending the universal spiritual and moral values along with the organisation of activities meeting the health maintenance and promotion values [5, p. 167].

Training of the teaching staff should be aimed at the formation of psychological and pedagogical competencies necessary for due interaction of educators with challenged learners. Training sessions with the participation of all actors of the educational relations are aimed at the development of skills intended to support others and engage in joint participation in different activities. The training format involves exercises for introducing and practising phrases such as: "Don't worry, you will succeed", "Let us work out the task together" and others. However, in this case, the environment does not create due conditions for ensuring the learner's psychological well-being: his/her subjective position is not fully manifested, and no conditions motivating the child for self-realisation and social activity are created [5].

The theoretical analysis of academic sources makes it possible to identify the following groups of an individual's risk behaviour determinants:

1. Psychophysiological characteristics of the personality. This group may include nervous system properties, the somatic status of the personality, the type of temperament, etc.
2. Cognitive characteristics of the personality. This group is represented by the general intellectual level, perceptual activity features, the maturity of perceptions, mental agility and flexibility of thinking, and the mental process development level.
3. Social characteristics of the personality. The group includes one's direct attitude towards objects and phenomena of the surrounding world and behavioural patterns of the social environment, as well as the perception of himself/herself and own behaviour.
4. Psychological characteristics of the personality. The group of presented determinants includes one's characterological features, self-esteem and self-perception, the level and quality of self-regulation, interests, value orientations, motivation, etc.
5. Cultural factors comprising traditions, communication, stereotypes and other cultural characteristics established in a particular locality.
6. Social factors. This group includes external characteristics: the reference group, social environment, upbringing types and scenarios, etc.

Summarising the above data, it seems reasonable to divide challenged learners' risk behaviour determinants in an inclusive educational environment into two groups: environment-induced and personality-related. Social/environmental factors of challenged learners' risk behaviour in an inclusive educational environment are determined by the factual promptness of the environment to provide the necessary support to learners with disabilities. Personality-induced factors correlate with the learner's readiness to accept the provided support, as well as the peculiarities of his/her perception of own somatic and mental resources and the specificity of the child's manifestation of his/her subjective position.

DISCUSSION

The implemented analysis of scientific research made it possible to identify the specificity and interrelation of environmental and personal determinants of risk behaviour affecting the psychological well-being of learners with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment and serving as risk factors represented in various components of this environment.

The identified constituent groups of personal determinants (psychophysiological, cognitive, social, and psychological characteristics) are manifested in a specific way in the personality of learners with limited health capacities. Along with biological agents, social and environmental factors influence the development of the personality and its psychological well-being in general. As concerns children of the target group, their biological factors (somatic condition, the psychophysical development level, and the nature of dysontogenesis) are largely determined by one's personal sphere with its specific features characterised, according to the research data analysed and presented in the article, by vulnerability, infantilism, victimhood, and susceptibility to the influence of negative factors of social environment and relevant instability.

The identification and description of the components of an inclusive educational environment and due consideration of the concepts presenting the peculiarities of psychophysical and personal development of challenged learners of different nosological groups enabled the authors to identify the specifics of environmental and personal determinants and formulate recommendations for educational psychologists, form masters, teachers and parents regarding prevention of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities.

The following is worth noting: the preventive work to overcome students' risk behaviour in an inclusive educational environment involves comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support. An important point is the observance of the principle of integration of diagnostics and rehabilitation in organising psychological and pedagogical councils, which makes it possible to effectively implement comprehensive support programmes for challenged students, organise activities aimed to overcome difficulties in learning, development, communication and behaviour, and to specify the content of risk behaviour prevention work in an educational organisation. This, as believed by the authors, is of particular importance for the prevention of risk behaviour of learners with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment and special education system.

CONCLUSION

The theoretical analysis made it possible to specify the general social and environmental determinants of risk behaviour manifested in an educational environment in general and specific to an inclusive educational environment, and to consider the personal determinants of such behaviour characteristic of learners with disabilities.

The study of inclusive educational environment components allowed the authors to find potentially negative factors of risk behaviour at each of the presented levels: social/communicative, informational, somatic, and objective. The specificity of these factors in relation to learners with disabilities in the conditions of inclusion is manifested individually in each case and depends on the impact of these determinants in the aggregate. The article provides specific examples of typical barriers (objective, communicative, and informational) manifested in an inclusive educational environment and representing potential risks of psychological distress in learners with limited health capacities in this environment.

In an inclusive educational environment, it is important to create conditions for directing the activity of persons prone to risk towards socially acceptable types of risk behaviour. The use of psychological and pedagogical support, social and pedagogical technologies in preventive work helps to prevent and reduce the risks of troubled behaviour in an inclusive educational environment and to increase the level of psychological well-being of challenged learners.

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Авторы

Семенова Елена Владимировна
(Россия, Екатеринбург)

Кандидат психологических наук, доцент кафедры специальной педагогики и специальной психологии, директор Института специального образования Уральского государственного педагогического университета
E-mail: iso.semenova@yandex.ru
ORCID ID: 0009-0007-5690-2686

Труфанова Галина Константиновна
(Россия, Екатеринбург)

Старший преподаватель кафедры специальной педагогики и специальной психологии Института специального образования Уральского государственного педагогического университета
E-mail: ya.trufanova-galina@yandex.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2288-433X

Бездетко Сергей Николаевич
(Россия, Екатеринбург)

Кандидат педагогических наук, доцент кафедры логопедии и клиники дизонтогенеза Института специального образования Уральского государственного педагогического университета
E-mail: s.n.bezdetko@mail.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2626-9799

Authors

Elena V. Semenova
(Russia, Yekaterinburg)

Cand. Sci. (Psychol.), Associate Professor of the Department of Special Pedagogy and Special Psychology, Director of the Institute of Special Education Ural State Pedagogical University
E-mail: iso.semenova@yandex.ru
ORCID ID: 0009-0007-5690-2686

Galina K. Trufanova
(Russia, Yekaterinburg)

Senior lecturer of the Department of Special Pedagogy and Special Psychology, Institute of Special Education Ural State Pedagogical University
E-mail: ya.trufanova-galina@yandex.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2288-433X

Sergey N. Bezdetko
(Russia, Yekaterinburg)

Cand. Sci. (Educ.), Associate Professor of the Department of Speech Therapy and Clinic of Dysontogenesis, Institute of Special Education Ural State Pedagogical University
E-mail: s.n.bezdetko@mail.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2626-9799

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Author's contribution

Elena V. Semenova: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision
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